
Morphologic Segmentation Linearity in Lang Leav's My Place in the Universe

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the textuality of Lang Leav's "My Place in the Universe", describing the morphologic segmentation linearity of its lexical and grammatical morphemes. Using a descriptive and structural analysis as the method in analyzing data, findings reveal that the prose contains fifty-four (54) lexical morphemes of twenty-four (24) simple form (roots), twenty-four (24) complex form (roots and affixations), six (6) compound words (two roots) and one (1) compound-complex form (two roots combined and affixation). Moreover, there are twenty-three (23) grammatical morphemes broken down into nine (9) prepositions, five (5) determiners, four (4) conjunctions, two (2) pronouns, two (2) modal verbs, and one (1) auxiliary verb. The results prove that Lang Leav's prose "My Place in the Universe" follows morphologic segmentation linearity in its narrative textuality. This study recommends that teaching and learning morphologic segmentation of words should be given attention not only by English teachers and language learners but also by every student since it is beneficial in language acquisition, vocabulary expansion, and reading comprehension. Language teachers should provide varied practical activities for students to have an in-depth understanding of lexical and grammatical morphemes. Further, it is also proposed that a morpho-syntactic structuration and linguistic investigation of the word formation process of words in the same piece should be conducted by future researchers.

KEYWORDS: morphology, structural analysis, segmentation linearity, lexical, grammatical.

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INTRODUCTION

Morphology is commonly defined as the study of the internal structure of words and the rules governing the formation of words in a language. A word is a unit of language that carries a separate and specific meaning, for example, the morpheme 're' which means again, back or to repeat. Some words preceded by 're' indicate that the action is being performed or described again (Global Montessori Network, 2023). When added to a word like 'read', it would lead to the formation of a new word which is 'reread' and one would know that this means 'to read again.' Our knowledge of words is a dynamic system in which we constantly create new words and even expand their meaning to new areas, rather than being a static system of information that relies on our memories. Thus, the English language is a complex system that requires mastery of various linguistic components, including morphology (Le, 2023).

Morphemes are parts of a word. According to Abeyweera (2020), morphemes are the smallest meaningful units in a language used in creating different forms of a word or a new word. There are two kinds of morphemes: the free morphemes and the bound morphemes. As discussed by Abdurrahman (2019), free morphemes can stand by themselves as words (read, swim, cook) while the bound morphemes such as -un, -im, and -ly are usually attached to a root, thereby causing a difference in the meaning or a change in the grammatical category of a word. Free morphemes can either be lexical or grammatical. Lexical morphemes or content words include nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs while grammatical morphemes or function words are pronouns, prepositions, determiners, conjunctions, interjections, and articles. On the other hand, inflectional and derivational morphemes are called bound morphemes. Inflectional morphemes do not change the grammatical category of a word such as the 's' for pluralization and 'ed' to indicate the past form of the verb while derivational morphemes such as -ly, -anti-, and -able change the syntactic category, and the meaning of the word they are attached to attached to. Having a sufficient knowledge of morphology helps an individual master a language, expand vocabulary, improve reading comprehension, and enhance the quality of one's writing.

Although there are previous studies that have explored the analysis of morphological and phonological segmentation in the

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English language, such as the Phonostylistic Analysis by F.H. Al-Hindawi and N.D. Hussien, (2020) about William Blake's Poem entitled "Cradle Song" and for instance, a Morphologic Segmentation Linearity in Aesop's Fable "The Farmer and the Snake" by Magdato (2024), linearity of morphemes and phonemes in the linguistic structure of the textuality of King Solomon's Book of Proverbs by de la Pena (2019) and another Morphologic Segmentation Linearity in Jose Garcia Villa's "PROEM" by Quebec (2022) where the same method was employed in analyzing different genres of text, there is still so much to be learned about morphologic segmentation since current researches on this area is still limited and further investigation is needed. Thus, this paper assumes that the linearity of morphemes and phonemes is revealed in the linguistic structure of the textuality of Lang Leav's My Place in the Universe.

The chosen selection of this linguistic inquiry is entitled "My Place in the Universe". It is a prose, written by Lang Leav and was published on her official Facebook page. It comprises two paragraphs with one hundred fourteen (114) words which will be the basis of textuality for structural analysis. This prose teaches us how to deal with a complex and inevitable unfolding of life's events, the radical power of destruction and rebirth, and deep acceptance of one's role in our universe. It invites readers to reflect on the purpose of each event in their lives, recognize the importance of each experience, and accept a journey with humility and admiration, believing they have a place and a role to play in this universe.

This research explores the morphologic segmentation linearity in the textuality of Lang Leav's prose "My Place in the Universe." With this study, language teachers will be more motivated to analyze morphologic forms more deeply to widen their knowledge and improve the quality of the teaching and learning process. Findings may also propel language learners to learn or develop new strategies that will help them develop their mastery and fluency of the language.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This linguistic inquiry investigates the morphologic segmentation linearity in Lang Leav's "My Place in the Universe." This study specifically focuses on analyzing the lexical and grammatical morphemes in the textuality of the prose, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of the text's overall form, and meaning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Morphologic segmentation breaks words into smaller units, known as morphemes, which bear meaning or grammatical function in a language (Poon et al., 2009). In linguistics, analyzing the structure of words is important to understand how words are formed and to uncover word meanings.

A study of morphologic segmentation linearity in the English language is essential for English teachers and learners alike, as it provides insight into the structure and organization of words in the language. According to Quebec (2022), analyzing words enables us to experience how to break apart unfamiliar words to understand their overall meaning and how a meaning associated with the word changes when affixes are added. Furthermore, developing an awareness of English morphology will enable language teachers to help their learners understand how words enter a language, what they consist of, and how they are formed by combining prefixes, suffixes, and roots (Öz, 2014).

This investigation argues that the prose "My Place in the Universe" by Lang Leav follows morphologic segmentation linearity in its narrative textuality. Morphology as the study of word structure is intimately related to language description and linguistic theory (Arkadiev & Klamer, 2016.) One linguistic theory that underpins this research is Corder's theory of linear grammar. This theory focuses on the structure of the sentence, treating the sentence as a string of grammatical categories like beads in a necklace, emphasizing the linear sequence of words in a sentence. This theory supports several linguistic researchers. For instance, the Syntactic Segmentation Linearity in Amador Daguio's "Man of Earth" by Cantina (2020), revealed that the lexical categories that make up the immediate constituents of the poem are nouns, verbs, determiners, auxiliaries, prepositions, conjunctions, adjectives, pronouns, adverbs, and interjections. Another study by de la Pena (2019) on the phonologic and morphologic analysis of King Solomon's Book of Proverbs revealed ninety free morphemes of fifty-two lexical morphemes and thirty-eight grammatical morphemes and forty bound morphemes of seventeen inflectional morphemes and twenty-three derivational morphemes. Similarly, the Morphologic Segmentation Linearity in Jose Garcia Villa's PROEM by Quebec (2022) revealed nineteen lexical morphemes and seven grammatical morphemes. Magdato (2024) also conducted a morphologic segmentation linearity in Aesop's Fable "The Farmer and the Snake," revealing thirty-two lexical morphemes and seventeen grammatical morphemes.

These studies employed structural analysis as the method for analyzing the chosen data and concluded that the chosen literary pieces follow a morphologic segmentation linearity in their free verse, and narrative textuality.

This linguistic inquiry synthesizes the morphologic segmentation linearity in the textuality of My Place in the Universe by Lang Leav. Further, this study would provide insights for language teachers on how to incorporate morphologic analysis in their teaching and for future researchers who would be interested in exploring more linguistic analysis like this one.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This paper employs descriptive analysis as the method of linguistic investigation. According to Loeb et al. (2017), descriptive analysis characterizes the world or phenomenon by identifying patterns in data to answer questions about who, what, where, when, and to what extent. This study will specifically focus on describing the language's lexical and grammatical category rather than how language is acquired or learned.

Since the textuality of the prose, *My Place in the Universe* will be divided into segments, fragments and categories, structural analysis will also be utilized. In linguistics, it is the analysis of a word, phrase, sentence, or longer unit in terms of its formal constituents (APA Dictionary of Psychology, 2018). Words are composed of a root and an affix such as prefixes, suffixes, infixes, and circumfixes. These parts of a word contribute to the totality of its meaning. Hence, this paper will analyze the words in the text according to their morphologic structure.

SOURCE OF DATA

The prose *My Place in the Universe* is chosen as the main data for this inquiry. It is ideal for this linguistic research since it is a single literary piece and not included in any of the author's published books. According to Abram and Harpham (2013), prose is an inclusive term for all discourse, spoken or written, which is not patterned into the lines of either metric verse or of free verse. In other words, it is not constrained by rhythmic and metrical patterns and other devices that structure poetry. It follows a grammatical structure organized into sentences and paragraphs to communicate messages, ideas, and expressions.

The text *My Place in the Universe* is written by Lang Leav and was published on her official Facebook page. Lang Leav is a novelist and poet, an international bestselling author, and winner of Qantas Spirit of Youth Award, Good Choice Award, and the coveted Churchill Fellowship. She has been featured in various international publications. Her works include her wide collection of prose and poetry such as *Love and Misadventure*, *Lullabies*, *Sea of Strangers*, *The Universe of Us*, *Love Looks Pretty on You*, *September Love*, *Memories*, *The Gift of Everything*, *Self-love for Small Town Girls* and her three novels, *Poemsia*, *Sad Girls* and *Others Were Emeralds*.

The words of the text appear below:

I feel my life culminating to a point, the delicate threads of existence joining to form a tapestry. The events up until the present that had seemed of no particular significance now imbued with a deeper, darker meaning.

I can see it so clearly—the greater plan. I understand that I am both the architect and tenant of my own destruction. I can feel it so acutely like an ache in my chest, knowing ultimately that I am locked into a chain of events that I cannot stop, an outcome I cannot alter, feeling at once helpless yet hopelessly awed by the part I will play in this beautiful, brutal expression of the Universe.

The prose is composed of two paragraphs with one hundred fourteen words which will be the basis for Morphologic Segmentation Linearity.

PROCEDURE

Several steps were undertaken in the conduct of Morphologic Segmentation Linearity in the textuality of Lang Leav's "My Place in the Universe." This includes three phases.

One: Selection of the Text

The researchers selected the prose entitled "My Place in the Universe" as the source of data after browsing through the author's official Facebook page.

Two: Segmentation of Morphologic Units

Identification of the content words in the textuality is done first. Then these words are segmented and categorized into their respective word class (Noun, Verb, Adjective or Adverb). They are also classified according to form such as simple, compound, complex, or compound-complex. The lexical morphemes are further analyzed according to their root and affixation.

The grammatical (function) morphemes are also identified, classified, and analyzed according to their constituents and functions in the sentences.

Three: Reporting of Findings

After the segmentation process, the lexical and grammatical morphemes will be presented in a table.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This linguistic inquiry focuses on the affixation structuration of the lexical and grammatical morphemes in the textuality of Lang Leav's *My Place in the Universe*.

The prose contains the following lexical morphemes.

Table 1. Lexical Morphemes in Lang Leav’s My Place in the Universe

Lexical Morphemes		Form	Root		Affixes
Feel	(V)	Simple	Feel		
Life	(N)	Simple	Life		
Culminating	(V)	Complex	Culminat (-e)		-ing
Point	(N)	Simple	Point		
Delicate	(ADJ)	Simple	Delicate		
Threads	(N)	Complex	Thread		-s
Existence	(N)	Complex	Exist		-ence
Joining	(N)	Complex	Join		-ing
Form	(V)	Simple	Form		
Tapestry	(N)	Simple	Tapestry		
Events	(N)	Complex	Event		-s
Up	(ADV)	Simple	Up		
Present	(N)	Simple	Present		
Seemed	(V)	Complex	Seem		-ed
No	(ADV)	Simple	No		
Particular	(ADJ)	Simple	Particular		
Significance	(N)	Complex	Signif (-y)		-cance
Now	(ADV)	Simple	Now		
Imbued	(V)	Complex	Imbue		-d
Deeper	(ADJ)	Complex	Deep		-er
Darker	(ADJ)	Complex	Dark		-er
Meaning	(N)	Complex	Mean		-ing
See	(V)	Simple	See		
So	(ADV)	Simple	So		
Clearly	(ADV)	Complex	Clear		-ly
Greater	(ADJ)	Complex	Great		-er
Plan	(N)	Simple	Plan		
Understand	(V)	Compound	Under-, -stand		
Architect	(N)	Compound	Archi-, -tect		
Tenant	(N)	Simple	Tenant		
Own	(ADJ)	Simple	Own		
Destruction	(N)	Complex	struct-	De-	-ion
Acutely	(ADV)	Complex	Cute	a-	-ly
Ache	(N)	Simple	Ache		
Knowing	(V)	Complex	Know		-ing
Ultimately	(ADV)	Complex	Ultimate		-ly
Am	(V)	Simple	Am		
Locked	(ADJ)	Complex	Lock		-ed
Chain	(N)	Simple	Chain		
Cannot	(V)	Compound	Can-, -not		
Stop	(V)	Simple	Stop		
Outcome	(N)	Compound	Out-, -come		
Alter	(V)	Simple	Alter		
Feeling	(V)	Complex	Feel		-ing
Once	(ADV)	Simple	Once		
Helpless	(ADJ)	Compound	Help-, -less		
Hopelessly	(ADV)	Compound-complex	Hope-, -less		-ly
Awed	(ADJ)	Complex	Awe		-d
Part	(N)	Simple	Part		
Play	(N)	Simple	Play		
Beautiful	(ADJ)	Complex	Beaut (-y)		-ful
Brutal	(ADJ)	Complex	Brut (-e)		-al
Expression	(N)	Complex	Press	Ex-	-ion
Universe	(N)	Compound	Uni-, -verse		

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There are twenty-three (24) simple forms of words made up of roots only. These are the verbs feel, form, see, am, stop, and alter; the adjectives delicate, own, and particular; the adverbs up, no, now, so, and once; and the nouns life, point, tapestry, present, plan, tenant, ache, chain, part and play. A root is the most basic form of a word that cannot be further divided into meaningful segments (Nikolopoulo, 2023). Root words can be added with affixes to pluralize singular words, form new meanings, and change the grammatical categories of words. Hu (2011) as mentioned in the study of Cao (2022), stated that it is a part of the word left when all affixes are removed. It helps students have a rational understanding of word formation and facilitates their vocabulary learning, memorization, word meaning guessing, and enlargement (Cao, 2022).

Lang Leav’s My Place in the Universe is also composed of twenty-four (24) complex forms of words. These are the verbs culminating, joining, seemed, imbued, knowing, and feeling; the adjectives deeper, darker, greater, locked, awed, beautiful, and brutal; the adverbs clearly, acutely, and ultimately; and the nouns threads, existence, events, significance, meaning, destruction, and expression. These words are made up of roots and inflectional and derivational affixes.

There are also six (6) compound forms of words, a result of merging two or more words to create a new and different word. These are the verbs understand and cannot; the adjective helpless and the nouns architect, outcome, and universe.

There is only one (1) compound-complex form of a word, the adverb hopelessly. This word is made up of two simple forms: the noun hope and the adjective less and the suffix -ly. The addition of the suffix -ly changed the category of the word from adjective to adverb.

Table 2. Grammatical Morphemes in Lang Leav’s My Place in the Universe

Grammatical Morphemes	Constituents	Functions in the Sentence
I	Pronoun	Refers to the subject or the speaker
My	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase my life
To	Preposition	Introduces the phrase to a point
A	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase a point
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the delicate threads
Of	Preposition	Introduces the phrase of existence joining
To	Preposition	Introduces the phrase to form a tapestry
A	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase a tapestry
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the events
Until	Preposition	Introduces the phrase until the present
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the present
That	Pronoun	Introduces the relative clause that had seemed of no particular significance
Had	Auxiliary Verb	Used as past perfect auxiliary form of the verb
Of	Preposition	Introduces the phrase of no particular significance
With	Preposition	Introduces the phrase with a deeper, darker meaning
A	Determiner	Marks the adjectives in a deeper, darker meaning
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
Can	Modal Verb	Used as a helping verb to the main verb can see
It	Pronoun	It refers to the greater plan
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the greater plan
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
That	Conjunction	Connects two independent clauses I understand and I am both the architect and tenant of my own destruction
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
Both	Conjunction	Links and emphasizes the two roles or positions (architect and tenant) that the speaker embodies
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the architect
And	Conjunction	Connects the phrases the architect and tenant of my own destruction
Of	Preposition	Introduces the phrase of my own destruction
My	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase my own destruction

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I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
Can	Modal Verb	Used as a helping verb to the main verb in can feel
It	Pronoun	Refers to the feelings described in like an ache
Like	Preposition	Introduces the phrase like an ache in my chest
An	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase an ache
In	Preposition	Introduces the phrase in my chest
My	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase my chest
That	Conjunction	Connects the clauses I can feel it so acutely like an ache in my chest knowing ultimately and I am locked into a chain of events that I cannot stop
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
Into	Preposition	Introduces the phrase into a chain of events
A	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase a chain
Of	Preposition	Introduces the phrase of events that I cannot stop
That	Conjunction	Connects the clauses I'm locked into a chain of events and I cannot stop
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
An	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase an outcome I cannot alter
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
At	Preposition	Introduces the phrase at once helpless
Yet	Conjunction	Connects the ideas helpless and hopelessly
By	Preposition	Introduces the phrase by the part I will play
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the part
I	Pronoun	Refers to the anonymous speaker
Will	Modal Verb	Used as a helping verb to the main verb in will play
In	Preposition	Introduces the phrase in this beautiful
This	Determiner	Marker of a noun in this beautiful, brutal expression
Of	Preposition	Introduces the phrase of the Universe
The	Determiner	Marker of a noun in the phrase the Universe

The prepositions TO, OF, UNTIL, WITH, LIKE, INTO, AT, IN, and BY introduce the prepositional phrases, indicating a direction and action in “to a point,” and “to form a tapestry”; to indicate possession or association in “of existence joining...,” “of no particular significance now imbued...,” “of my own destruction,” “of events I cannot stop”; to indicate a point in time in “until the present that had seemed...”; to indicate connection or accompaniment in “with a deeper, darker meaning”; to establish a similarity in “like an ache”; to indicate a direction towards something like in “ in my chest” and “into a chain of events that I cannot stop”; to indicate a state in “at once helpless yet hopelessly...” and to indicate the cause in “by the part I will play...”.

The word ‘MY’ in the first and second paragraphs functions as a determiner of words like “life” (my life), “own” (own destruction), and “chest” (my chest). The morpheme ‘A’ functions as a determiner and is used as a marker of the nouns as shown in the phrases “a point,” “a tapestry,” “a deeper, darker meaning,” and “a chain of events...” in sentence 2 of the second paragraph. The determiner ‘AN’ in the second paragraph is used as a marker of the noun in the phrases “an ache” and “an outcome.” The determiner ‘THE’ is used to refer to a noun in the phrases “the delicate threads...,” “the present,” “the greater plan,” “the part” and “the Universe.” The morpheme ‘THIS’ in the second paragraph functions as a determiner, referring to the noun phrase “beautiful, brutal expression of the Universe.”

The conjunction THAT connects the subordinate clause to the main clause; the conjunction BOTH connects two noun phrases “the architect” and “tenant” while AND links two nouns together indicating the simultaneous role played by the speaker. The morpheme YET is used to connect the words “helpless” and “hopelessly” to show the contrasting emotions or feelings of the speaker.

The pronoun “I” found in both paragraphs refers to the speaker while the “it” in the second paragraph refers to something not explicitly mentioned in the text.

The modal verbs ‘CAN’ and ‘WILL’ intensified the meaning of the main verbs “can” and “will” while the auxiliary verb ‘HAD’ indicates a past form.

CONCLUSION

A word may belong to a certain word class but its function and meaning changes when used together with other words in different contexts or when added with affixes. Therefore, morphological segmentation is important. Breaking down the internal structure of words helps in understanding how words are formed or constructed and how the specific function of different morphemes contributes to the overall form and meaning of the text. When there is sufficient knowledge of morphology, language learners will experience an increase in their vocabulary and reading comprehension (Quebec, 2022.)

Based on the analysis and findings, it is revealed that Lang Leav's *My Place in the Universe* has fifty-four (54) lexical morphemes of twenty-four (24) simple forms (roots), twenty-four (24) complex forms, made up of roots and affixations, six (6) compound words, formed by combining two roots and one (1) compound-complex form (two roots combined and affixation). It also contains twenty-three (23) grammatical morphemes broken down into nine (9) prepositions, five

(5) determiners, four (4) conjunctions, two (2) pronouns, two (2) modal verbs, and one (1) auxiliary verb.

Due to these findings, it can be concluded that "My Place in the Universe" by Lang Leav follows morphologic segmentation linearity in its narrative textuality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In coherence with the findings and conclusion of this linguistic inquiry, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teaching and learning morphologic segmentation of words should be given attention not only by English teachers and language learners but also by every student since it is beneficial in language acquisition, vocabulary expansion, and reading comprehension.
2. Language teachers must provide varied activities for students to have an in-depth understanding of lexical and grammatical morphemes in a sentence or text.
3. Future researchers may conduct morpho-syntactic structuration and linguistic research focusing on the word formation process of words found in the same piece or other bodies of work by the same author.

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